

Interview guide

Note of the authors: The researchers used this document as a tool to guide the semi-structured interviews based on the themes listed below. Rather than following a pre-determined script, the interviewer selected, rephrased or proposed additional questions whenever it was appropriate to continue with the discussion.

Introduction

Thank you for the time and opportunity to have this interview.

The purpose of this research is to understand whether and how your information systems are being integrated with other organizations in the construction and real estate industry, and what technologies are currently being used to facilitate those inter-organizational integrations.

Basic definitions (*Explain only if necessary*):

- Inter-organizational integration: Implementing or using solutions across the boundaries of multiple autonomous organizations. In this context, integration is achieved mainly through technology, but it also involves the business and socio-organizational aspects
- Information systems: We are looking into the systems that handle information which can be considered essential for your own business and the industry overall, including enterprise systems and software platforms

We expect this interview to last between 45 minutes and one-hour, maximum. We will start with some general questions about your background and then we will talk more about the current business context and the technological state-of-the-art.

(Hand out and explain the consent information sheet):

This interview is confidential, so all answers will be kept anonymous. Any interview fragments that become part of our final report cannot be traced back to the individual participants. Only the members of our research group can review the notes or interview transcripts, and these are not shared with any other external people. You can skip any question if you do not know the answer, or prefer not to answer, and you are also free to withdraw from the study anytime.

Questions about the interviewee background

- What is your name?
- What is your job title?
- How long have you been working in the company and in your current position?
- Can you briefly describe some of your main tasks and responsibilities?

Questions about the research topic

- How would you describe the current status of the construction and real estate industry in Finland, when it comes to the integration of information and systems across different organizations?
- What types of land, building, property or real estate data have you integrated into your information systems?
- What types of data are still handled in paper or blueprints?

- During which stages of the built environment life-cycle do you collect data (e.g. planning, design, construction, operation and maintenance, etc.)?
- Which information are you sharing with any other public or private organizations and how?
- How do you collaborate or integrate with other actors in the public and private sector?
- Can you tell me more about a past or ongoing inter-organizational systems integration project in which you have participated?
 - o What technical challenges have you experienced or needed to be solved for this project?
 - o What non-technical challenges have you experienced or needed to be solved for this project?

Closure

- Would you like to comment any additional thoughts or ideas you have about the topics we discussed during this interview?
- Do you know any other person inside the company or among your partners that we can interview next?